

Optically Active Tertiary Alcohols Containing Two Equal Groups

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Optically active tertiary alcohols containing two equal groups have been obtained by the action of α -(+)-2-methylbutylethyl acetate and the appropriate Grignard complexes, R.Mg.X (where R = Me, Et, Prⁿ, Prⁱ, Buⁿ, or Ph).

Frankland and Twiss¹ studied the action of ester of optically active hydroxy-acids on the Grignard reagent. Bergmann and Hartrott² obtained an optically inactive product from an active ester with phenylmagnesium bromide. To explain this it has been suggested that the carbinol formed undergoes spontaneous reversible dehydration, resulting in the loss of activity, as shown below.

Kenyon and Campbell³ and Thakar and Vasi⁴, however, obtained optically active tertiary alcohols by treating phenylmagnesium bromide with (—)-methyl hydratropate and ethyl lactate respectively. To confirm whether similar condensations between other optically active esters, like α -(+)-2-methylbutylethyl acetate, and the appropriate Grignard complexes afford optically active tertiary alcohols containing two equal groups or not, the present investigation has been undertaken. Arnold *et al*.⁵ have shown that esters of the type;

are cleaved abnormally by the Grignard reagent if R contains substituents which sterically hinder additions to the carbonyl group of the ester and if R' is of such a nature that it has considerable thermodynamic stability as cation (R'⁺). In the present investigation, optical activity has been found to be retained in spite of the molecular rearrangement.

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 1936.
2. *Ibid.*, 1935, 1218.
3. *Ibid.*, 1941, 436.
4. *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1961, 20B, 66.
5. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 3444.

For the preparation of optically active tertiary carbinols, the ester of α -(+)-2-methylbutylethyl acetate and the Grignard reagent R. Mg. X (in which R represents Me, Et, Prⁿ, Prⁱ, Buⁿ or Ph) were taken. Instead of the usual method, the appropriate Grignard reagent after its preparation was heated on a water bath and the complex taken in benzene and to this the ester in benzene solution was added. This improved the yield considerably. The active tertiary alcohols prepared are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	Tertiary alcohol.	B. p./ 15mm.	d^{25} .	n_D^{25} .	% Yield.	$[\alpha]_D^{25}$ ($l=0.5$).	Found.	Reqd.
1	1,1-Dimethyl-1-ol-M	145-50°	0.9851	1.4202	80.1	+3.05°	C : 74.82 % H : 13.67	74.82% 13.60
2	1,1-Diethyl-1-ol-M	175-80°	0.9853	1.4313	66.4	+2.12°	C : 76.63 H : 13.73	76.76 13.95
3	1,1-Di- <i>n</i> -propyl-1-ol-M	193-95°	0.9764	1.4331	57.3	+2.29	C : 77.66 H : 13.81	78.00 14.00
4	1,1-Di-isopropyl-1-ol-M	175-77°	0.9746	1.4302	33.3	+3.18°	C : 77.55 H : 13.61	78.00 14.00
5	1,1-Di- <i>n</i> -butyl-1-ol-M	230-35°	0.9827	1.4341	32.7	+2.01°	C : 78.23 H : 13.61	78.96 14.04
6	1, 1-Diphenyl-1-ol-M	270-80°	1.1454	1.5402	53.9	+3.59°	C : 84.29 H : 8.55	85.07 8.98

*M denotes -2-(β -methylbutyl)ethane.

EXPERIMENTAL

α -(+)-2-Methylbutyl Malonate.—To sodium (99.0 g.), dissolved in anhydrous ethanol (1250 ml) and heated to 60°, diethyl malonate (630.0 g.) was added slowly. The temperature was then raised to 80° and α -(+)-1-bromo-2-methylbutane⁶ (580 g., $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 1.07^\circ$) was slowly added (3 hr.). The mixture was heated on the water-bath for 1 hr., the ethanol distilled, and the residue decomposed by the usual method. The ethereal extract was washed with water, dried, ether evaporated, and distilled at 180-210°/15mm; yield 50%, d^{25} 1.1275, n_D^{25} 1.4220, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 4.19^\circ$ ($l, 0.5$). Lit.⁷ reports d^{20} 0.9666 and $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 7.19^\circ$.

α -(+)-2-Methylbutylethyl Acetate: (a). α -(+)-2-Methylbutylacetic Acid.—The preceding ester (475.0 g.) was slowly added to a three-neck flask fitted with a stirrer, condenser, and a separating funnel and containing a solution (hot) of KOH (475 g. in 475 ml water). On the completion of the addition of the ester, the content of the flask was diluted with water (475 ml) and distilled to remove the ethanol so formed. To the residue cold sulphuric acid solution (413 g. acid in 1060 ml water) was added and the content refluxed for 3-4 hr. The organic acid was extracted with ether and the ethereal extract washed with water, dried, and distilled under reduced pressure to obtain α -(+)-2-methyl-

6. Thakar and Vasi, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1960, **19B**, 322.

7. Walden, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1906, **55**, 11.

butylacetic acid, b.p. 200-205°/15mm, yield 75.0%, d_{25}^{25} 1.0637, n_D^{25} 1.1417; $[\alpha]_D^{25} +4.49^\circ$ (l , 0.5); M.W. 129.4 ($C_7H_{14}O_2$ requires M.W. 130.0).

(b). α -(+)-2-Methylbutylethyl Acetate.—A mixture of the preceding acetic acid (200 g.), anhydrous ethanol (666 ml), and H_2SO_4 (conc., 5 ml) was refluxed for 5-6 hr. The excess of the ethanol was distilled; the contents of the flask were poured into water, extracted with ether, and the ethereal extract was washed with sodium carbonate solution (10%) and then with water; it was dried and the solvent removed to provide the ester which distilled under reduced pressure; b.p. 145-60°/10mm, yield 74.4%, d_{25}^{25} 1.0146, n_D^{25} 1.1413, $[\alpha]_D^{25} +3.24^\circ$. (Found: C, 68.12; H, 11.11. $C_9H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 68.34; H, 11.39%).

Preparation of Optically Active Tertiary Carbinols.— α -(+)-2-Methylbutylethyl acetate (0.5M), dissolved in benzene (60 ml), was added dropwise during 3 hr. to a benzene solution of the Grignard complex (R. Mg. X, where R is Me, Et, Prⁿ, Prⁱ, Buⁿ or Ph). (The complex was prepared in ether, the ethereal solution evaporated on a water bath, and the complex taken in 60 ml of benzene). On completion of the reaction, the benzene layer separating was shaken successively with water, sodium carbonate solution (5%), and ether and dried. On evaporation of the solvent, the residual optically active tertiary active alcohols were obtained in respective cases. These were purified by distillation under vacuum.

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